

TWO CONJECTURES CONCERNING EXTENTS OF SMARANDACHE FACTOR PARTITIONS

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Abstract . In this paper we verify two conjectures concerning extents of Smarandache factor partitions .

Key words . Smarandache factor partition , sum of length .

Let p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n be distinct primes , and let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n be positive integers . Further , let

$$(1) \quad t = p_1^{a_1} p_2^{a_2} \cdots p_n^{a_n} ,$$

and let $F(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ denote the number of ways in which t could be expressed as the product of its divisors . Furthermore , let

$$(2) \quad F(1\#n) = F(\underbrace{1, 1, \dots, 1}_{n \text{ ones}}) .$$

If d_1, d_2, \dots, d_r are divisors of t and

$$(3) \quad t = d_1 d_2 \cdots d_r ,$$

then (3) is called a Smarandache factor partition representation with length r . Further , let $\text{Extent}(F(1\#n))$ denote the sum of lengths of all Smarandache factor partition representations of $p_1 p_2 \cdots p_n$. In [2] , Murthy proposed the following two conjectures .

Conjecture 1 .

$$(4) \quad \text{Extent}(F(1\#n)) = F(1\#(n+1)) - F(1\#n) .$$

Conjecture 2 .

$$(5) \quad \sum_{k=0}^n \text{Extent}(F(1\#n)) = F(1\#(n+1)).$$

In this paper we verify the mentioned conjectures as follows.

Theorem. For any positive integer n , the identities (4) and (5) are true.

Proof. Let $Y(n)$ be the n -th Bell number. By the definitions of $F(1\#n)$ and $Y(n)$ (see [1]), we have

$$(6) \quad F(1\#n) = Y(n).$$

Let $L(r)$ be the number of Smarandache factor partitions of $p_1 p_2 \dots p_n$ with length r . Then we have

$$(7) \quad L(r) = S(n, r),$$

where $S(n, r)$ is the Stirling number of the second kind with parameters n and r . Since

$$(8) \quad Y(n) = \sum_{r=1}^n S(n, r),$$

by (6), (7) and (8), we get

$$(9) \quad F(1\#n) = Y(n) = \sum_{r=1}^n S(n, r)$$

and

$$(10) \quad \text{Extent} F(1\#n) = \sum_{r=1}^n r S(n, r).$$

It is a well known fact that

$$(11) \quad r S(n, r) = S(n+1, r) - S(n, r-1),$$

for $n \geq r \geq 1$ (see [1]). Notice that $S(n, n) = 1$. Therefore, by (9), (10) and (11), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Extent}(F(1\#n)) = \sum_{r=1}^n (S(n+1,r) - S(n,r-1)) \\
(12) \quad & = \sum_{r=1}^n S(n+1,r) - \sum_{r=1}^n S(n,r-1) = (Y(n+1)) - S(n+1,n+1) \\
& \quad - (Y(n) - S(n,n)) = Y(n+1) - Y(n) = F(1\#(n+1)) - F(1\#n).
\end{aligned}$$

It implies that (4) holds.

On the other hand, we get from (4) that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{k=0}^n \text{Extent}(F(1\#k)) = 1 + \sum_{r=1}^n \text{Extent}(F(1\#r)) \\
(13) \quad & = \sum_{r=1}^n (F(1\#(r+1)) - F(1\#r)) = F(1\#(n+1)).
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, (5) is also true. The theorem is proved.

References

- [1] C. Jordan, Calculus of Finite Differences, Chelsea, 1965.
- [2] A. Murthy, Length/extent of Smarandache factor partitions, Smarandache Notions J. 11(2000), 275-279.

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